

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14714385

Effect of Task Repetition on Working Memory among Students with Working Memory deficit at Government Day Junior Secondary School Yarimaram Potiskum Yobe State

¹GARBA Bala Nata'ala & ²ISA Abdulmumini

¹Department of Special Education,
Bayero University Kano, Nigeria

²Department of Primary Education Studies,
Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State, Nigeria
Phone: 08032079912

ABSTRACT

A functional working memory is vital for student's learning, deficit in working memory means difficulties with various learning skills. Repeating a task means to get perfect with it. This research employed a pretest- post-test experimental-control group quasi-experimental design to determine the effect of task repetition on junior secondary two students of Government Day Junior Secondary school Yarimaram Potiskum Yobe State. One research question and one hypothesis were set to guide the research, the sample size of the study was 40 students. The data collection instruments were working memory rating scale for identification of students with working memory difficulties and working memory test. The instruments were both adapted and modified and subjected to validity and reliability tests, both validity and reliability index were determined. The data obtained during the study were analyzed using Analysis of variance ANOVA in order to test the null hypothesis. The study found a significant mean difference between the experimental and control groups scores of the students after exposure to task repetition strategy. The study recommends that task repetition should be adopted in teaching working memory skills in junior secondary schools

Keywords: Task repetition, working memory, working memory deficit

INTRODUCTION

Teaching students with working memory deficits require special approaches that directly target those deficits. In recent years, task repetition has drawn much attention as an important aspect of teaching targeting working memory deficits, since it is considered primarily useful in making learners alter their working memory strategies for better learning. The saying that "practice makes perfect" illustrate a well knowing fact that task repetition makes perfect. Task repetition according to Encyclopedia almanacs (2021) has been discussed by several medieval thinkers but demonstrated empirically by Hemann Ebbinghus in 1885. Ebbinghus demonstrated that retention of information improves as functions of number of times the information has been studied. Repetition was believed to be reminiscent of behaviorists' drills that are based on the assumption that learning occurs via a process of habit formation through repetition.

Task repetition as a concept is not easily amenable to a clear definition or description. While the research on task repetition is minimal, task repetition is used for a variety of purposes. Such variations from research-based to pedagogical, coupled with such variables as task type and task conditions, make it extremely difficult to establish an all encompassing definition. As the concept implies, repetition does not necessarily mean reading the same story or completing the same activity, over and over again. Instead, repetition refers to any form of work that provides the child with opportunities to practice a skill or knowledge area. The science behind repetition is that, learning requires electrical energy to create neural connections. The less automatic something is; the more energy is required to create the connection. These neural connections in children are only beginning to be formed. Repetition is the necessary building block that allows them to strengthen the connections in the brain that help them learn. (Montessori Academy 2021). According to Moser (2018), task repetition as a pedagogy was first conceptualized by Bygate and Samuda (2005). They define task repetition as repetition of the same or slightly altered tasks whether whole task or parts of the task. Bygate and Samuda (2005) further identifies real task repetition as the kind experienced by learners when they find themselves repeatedly in highly similar communication situations and with the opportunity to build on their previous attempt at completing the task.

As the saying goes, practice makes perfect. Indeed, to master a skill, a learner typically needs to practice it time and again so that conscious processes, which are monitored and can result in cognitive overload, become automated in the long run (Zaccaron 2019). Ellis (2009) perceived task repetition to have involved asking learners to repeat the same or slightly altered task (whole or part of the task) at certain interval. It can also be described as repeating the same task with the same content or repeating the task with the same procedure but with different content.

Task repetition involves phases. According to Ahmadian (2012), the first performance of the task is the preparation for further performance. He argued that, to handle a task at hand, the preparation allow the students to simultaneously focus their attention on the message content, scan their memory and seek appropriate language resource for use. The first encounter enables them to establish familiarity with the task and or content moreover. The familiarity provides them with the bases to handle subsequent task more accurately and efficiently. Researches in task repetition have come up with various types of task repetition.

The Concept of Working Memory

Working memory was sometimes referred to as short term memory. Cowan (2017) says; working memory is a system of components that holds a limited amount of information temporarily in a heightened state of availability for use in ongoing processing. The definition does not depend on statements about the exact organization of components that may store or process information which made working memory defy single definition. According to Zhang (2019), short-term or working memory acts as a kind of "scratch-pad" for temporary recall of the information which is being processed at any point in time, and has been referred to as the brain's "Post-it note". According to Ogunleye, Lawal, & Obateru (2020) working memory is the ability to remember and process information at the same time. It holds a small amount of information (typically around 7 items or even less) in mind in an active, readily-available state for a short period of time (typically from 10 to 15 seconds, or sometimes up to a minute).

The term working memory was generally associated with the work of Baddeley 1974's memory research where it viewed the short-term memory to be too simplistic and therefore replaced it with working memory and proposed that working memory has the following characteristics:

- a. phonological loop; (stores and consolidate new words) which is a short-term verbal store that holds verbal material in a buffer. The information can be kept active through sub vocal rehearsal.
- b. The visuospatial sketchpad; (create and manipulate visuospatial representation) is a short-term store for visual and spatial material. It is believed to be essential for mental imagery and spatial reasoning.
- c. The episodic buffer; (stores and integrate information from different source) is a temporary store that integrates information from the phonological loop, the visuospatial sketchpad, and long-term memory.
- d The central executive; (for attention control) is the master component that coordinates activities among the phonological loop, the visuospatial sketchpad, and the episodic buffer. The central executive is

believed to allocate attention and direct cognitive efforts. It is believed to be mediated by the frontal lobes of the brain.

Working memory according to Nwaze and Nwani (2020) enable the maintenance of information in mind while acting with the information to guide actions. According to Adubasin (2018) working memory help students to store information in their minds for a short period of time which was useful in thinking. It is therefore central to the ability to select and implement goal-directed behavior, to exercise what are termed executive functions. It is usually assumed that the short-term memory spontaneously decays over time. However, it can be extended by repetition or rehearsal (either by reading items out loud, or by mental stimulation).

Working Memory Difficulties

Working memory difficulties are common features of wide range of developmental disorders and specific learning disabilities including attention deficit and hyper activity disorders ADHD, dyslexia, specific language impairment and as well as mathematical difficulties. They can also occur in absence of any diagnosed disorder and present a significant risk factor for poor educational progress (Holmes 2012).

According to McCoy, Conrad, Richman, Napoulos, and Bell (2013), working memory difficulties may be attributed to premature birth, low birth weight, neonatal insult (head injury) and maternal education. They believed that children with working memory disorders may have visual memory deficit, phonological deficit, verbal blending of visual information problems, that working memory in children are mostly prone to diagnosed as attention deficit or behavior problem. In addition, Holmes (2012) posited that this children have poor academic progress, difficulty following multi-step instruction, failing to complete common classroom activities that require large amount of information to be held in the mind, ,problem in keeping their place in demanding and complex activities such as writing, and high level if inattentive and distractible behavior.

Working memory deficit impacts negatively on children especially those demanding school activities. A child has to read, comprehend, and integrate an information read to uncover the meaning relies heavily on child's ability to simultaneously process and store information over the short term. Similarly following a set of complex instructions, which a child would often have to do in the classroom, relies on the ability to remember the different parts of the instruction while carrying out various steps to complete the action successfully. (Adubasin 2018)

According to Holmes, Gathercole and Dunning (2010), children with poor working memory carry out the first command of a multi step instruction skip straight to the last or simply abandon all the tasks as they are unable to remember all the sequence. They make characteristic errors in their class work; they make mistakes in writing and counting. In their written work, they miss out letters, skip a whole word or blend part of the different word from different sentence. Example, in writing the sentence "my holiday 17th June" they will write "my holune". In counting task, they lose track on the number they work with. Example, if they are adding number like 28, 7, and 11, they miss out the "7" and add together 28 and 11. These children fail to self-correct themselves. It is worthy of note therefore that with the heavy working memory demand of classroom activities and instruction, it is not surprising that one of the key characteristics of children with working memory deficit is poor educational attainment.

Working Memory Assessments

Although working memory is a memory type that have its own models on which children's memory ability could be measured, Mangal (2018) stated that on general bases, the soundness or quality of one's memory can be judged on the basis of his power of retention. How properly a child can retain or store learnt things in his memory may provide a basis for the measurement of the ability and capacity of one's memory. That the formula for memory storage capacity is the amount learnt minus amount forgotten.

Until recently, working memory is tested using the various intelligent tests from the early days of cognitive psychology. Examples of such tests were Benet and Simson intelligent scale developed in 1905 and Wechsler intelligent test developed in 1939. Recently several intelligent tests were reviewed to

include working memory test. Similarly, comprehensive working memory batteries were developed in recent times. Although a comprehensive working memory assessment and related cognitive process is recommended, when children are referred to learning problem, the informal method and standardized tests should vary depending on the area of concern and the age of the children and the measurement tool available. (Malekpour, Aghababaei and Abedi 2013).

Recently, test like working memory test batteries for children (WMTB-C) according to Holmes and Gathercole (2012) is the only norm referenced test developed based on Baddeley's working memory norms. Another test is Automated Working memory Assessment which is computer based assessment developed in the United kingdom for age 4-22. In the same vein, Holmes, Gathercole and Dunning (2010) opined that working memory rating scale can also be used to identify children with working memory impairment. The scale is a behavioral rating scale consisting of 22 statements which are rated by the child's teacher. It provides quick and efficient method for the early identification of working memory problems in a school. Therefore teachers can use the scale as part of their routine students' working memory evaluation in their classes for better understanding of their problems.

Working Memory Intervention

Working memory intervention in schools as suggested by Holmes, Gathercole and Dunning (2010) should focus on reducing the memory load of the child in classroom, direct memory improving strategies or activities in the classroom, and directly training memory through repeated practice on working memory tasks. Teaching strategies to improve performance in working memory tasks such as rehearsals, chunking and meta-cognitive strategies, is the first and the most basic component to improve memory. These strategies are usually developed without explicit instructions or training. Serial repetitive process allows information to be maintained in working memory for a longer period of time. Meta-cognitive strategy training involves teaching of strategies relating to a specific, cognitive, behavioral and academic task. It also involves mnemonics as well (Malekpour, Aghababaei & Abedi 2013). In the same vein, Alloway (2006) suggested seven principle on which working memory intervention and instruction should be based. The first is to educate teachers on working memory and to recognize children experiencing working memory difficulties. Teachers should be aware on the context the working memory play in every day classroom activities and to emphasize that working memory failure are sometimes associated with inattentive behavior.

The second principle is to monitor how children with working memory difficulties cope with challenging activities in the classroom. this therefore help in detecting the early warning signs of memory failure and in this way teachers can simply understand whether children do forget a crucial steps in a given classroom task or not.

The third principle focuses on teachers evaluating learning activities to identify those that will be problematic for children with poor working memory capacity. This includes activities that are very long, those that are meaningless or involves unfamiliar materials and those that are complex involving significant memory processing. The fourth step focuses on teachers developing instruction activity that reduces the memory load of the children. This can be done by reducing the amount of information a child has to remember, increasing the familiarity and meaningfulness of the material children are working with, and simplifying complex activities. Teachers can do this by reducing the steps in an activity, and breaking down activities into shorter activities, relating new materials to previously acquired knowledge, simplifying linguistic structures, and reducing length of complex sentences used to explain complex activities.

The fifth principle targets the profound difficulties children with poor working memory experience when trying to remember instruction and task information. It encourages teacher to frequently repeat important information including classroom management information, task specific instruction, and detail information intrinsic to an activity.

The last two principles centers on how children will help themselves. The sixth is for the teachers to provide and promote the use of memory aids such as wall charts and posters, list of useful spelling and personalized dictionaries, counters, number lines multiplication grid, calculations memory cards and

audio recorder. The seventh is that children with working memory difficulties should be supported to develop their own strategies to support their weak memory skills. This strategy involves the students asking for help, rehearsing important information, note-taking, making links between previously learned activity to activate support from long-term memory, and place-keeping and organizational strategies such as using flow charts and diagrams. In sum, the memory instruction should be part of routine teacher training focusing on early identification and immediate intervention.

Statement of the problems

Working memory is regarded as the sketchpad of the students, deficits in working memory means students have difficulties with classroom multitask activities, he/she may easily forget instruction, hate any cognitively challenging tasks they have difficulty copying from chalk board in to their note books, have place keeping errors, and have difficulty understanding context in stories. Those students do not engage in classroom discussions. These in turn stand on the way of students learning and overall academic and social pursuit. Several factors could be behind poor students working memory ranging from; poor instruction, poor school readiness, as well as poor knowledge of working memory problems from the teachers. Despite the toll of working memory deficits on students, these students can develop and attain their full potentials with appropriate and validated intervention that addresses directly those areas of difficulties. More specifically repetitive task practice which offer students another opportunity to relearn a previously less understood classroom learning tasks.

Purpose of the study

This study unfolds some useful insights on how task repetition can be applied on students with working memory difficulties in classes. It demonstrated that the repetition of working memory task could increase working memory abilities of learners to a greater extent.

Research Questions

What is the effect of task repetition on working memory of student of Government day junior secondary school Yarimaram Potiskum?

Hypothesis

There is no significant mean difference in the both pretest and post-test mean scores of the students in working memory.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed an experimental-control group quasi-experimental design where the participants were purposefully sampled. Only the students typical to the research objectives were selected. The population of the study constituted all the JSS two students of the school. The sample size constitute 20 students both male and females.

Instrumentation

The data collection instruments of this research includes: Working memory Rating scale for the initial identification of the students with working memory difficulties and working memory test adapted from Alloway (2008) automated working test manual published by Pearson education Inc.

Procedure for Data collection

The researcher administered both the instruments in order to identify and assess the students respectively. The assessments was performed twice first before intervention and the second which was post-test, after intervention in both the experimental and control groups

Method of Data Analysis

This study used Analysis of variance ANOVA statistics to determine the effect of task repetition on students working memory.

RESULTS

The research hypothesis

There is no significant mean difference in the pretest and post-test mean scores of the students in working memory.

Table 1: ANOVA Result on post-test scores of the students in working memory areas.

Variables	Test	Ss	Df	Ms	F value	P value	Sig.	Decision
Phonological Wm	Between group	145.833	2	72.9166				
Visual wm	Within group	228.5	57	4.008	18.19	0.0000	0.05	Rejected
Central Executive wm	Total	374.333						

The table above indicates that the data was analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistics, the result revealed that the sum square between groups and within groups are 145.833 and 228.5 respectively, while sum square total was 374.333 mean while the mean square between groups are 72.9166 and that of within groups are 4.008. The calculated F-value is 18.19 with the p-value of 0.000, 2 and 57 degree of freedom. Consequently the result favors alternate hypothesis that there is significant difference in the working memory performance of the students in the 3 working memory areas. As a result of their exposure to a repetitive task practice strategy.

Moreover, in order to determine the differences among the students in the 3 working memory areas. A SCHEFE test was performed on STATA the result revealed that the students mean scores compared between listening recall (Phonological memory) and word recall (Visuo-sketch pad memory) have the mean contrast of 1.25 with the p-value of 0.128. This signifies that there is no significant difference because the p. value is 0.128 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, the mean contrast between Dot matrix (central executive) and word recall (Visuo-sketch pad) was 3.75 with p-value 0.000. This reveals that a significant difference exist because the p. value 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. In the same vein, the contrast between Dot matrix (central executive) and listening recall (Phonological) is 2.5 with p-value of 0.001. This also shows that a significant difference exist in the performance of the students in the areas as a result of their exposure to repetitive task practice.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The research Hypothesis which was to determine the effect of task repetition on working memory areas, the finding on the table above revealed that the sum square between and within groups were 145.833 and 374.333. The mean square between and within groups are 72.9166 & 4.008 respectively the f-value is 18.19. While the p-value is 0.000 at 0.05 level of significance. Consequently the table revealed that there exist a significant differences in the performance of the students in the 3 working memory area after exposure to task repetition strategy.

The compared means of phonological memory and visuo-sketch pad memory have 1.25 contrast with p-value 0.128. This signifies that there is no significant difference in the working memory performance of the students in the two areas because p-value of 0.128 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, the mean contrast between central executive and visual-sketchpad was 3.75 p value 0.000. This shows that a significant difference exist because the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. In the same vein, the mean contrast between central executive and phonological working memory is 2.5 with p-value 0.001 at 0.05 level of significance. This also signifies that a significant variation exist in their performance in the two areas. This research finding corresponds with Alessandra, and Klaus (2022). Amundsen, Germanslund, & Stokke (2014) who found that repetition create in working memory a retrieval practice, increases the probability of recognition of learnt tasks which in turn makes cumulative learning more likely. Similarly Ackerman, Beier, and Boyle (2002). Found that students performed better in spatial test. Listening test and word recall with 6.72 63 and 60 respectively based on the items of the working memory test administered.

CONCLUSION

Students ability to learn effectively depend on a functional working memory, this research through the use of working memory rating scale and working memory test generated data and analyzed using analysis of variance statistics discovered that task repetition technique was effective in students with working memory deficit.

RECOMMENDATION

This research recommends that task repetition strategy should be used by teachers in teaching students working memory skills

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